

Censorship As Information Behavior

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ABSTRACT

Censorship may be explained through the lens of information behavior. In particular, the theory of information worlds states that information forms the small social worlds of individuals, influencing both what information they access, as well as what information they share. Thus, small worlds censorship can occur when small worlds' actions shape policy in the larger lifeworld, reflecting the information behaviors of collective individuals who believe that their values are the "right values." This phenomenon is happening in real time as school and public libraries face an unprecedented number of book challenges and bans that predominately target materials with themes related to the LGBTQ+ and BIPOC experience. If small worlds censorship actions lead to the passing of local laws so that certain cultural goods are removed from public institutions and consequently, books are withheld preventing members of the library's community from reading freely, then book banning is harmful in multiple, abusive manners. One of the most important tools in the library's fight against censorship is a strong selection policy, which also has the effect of shaping information behavior. This conceptual paper explores censorship through the lens of information behavior, practice, and policy.

KEYWORDS

Censorship; information behavior; information worlds; libraries; collection development policy

INTRODUCTION

Taking a broad view on censorship, the American Library Association (2012) includes in its definition any attempt by an individual or group to restrict or remove materials from the public, as well as the outright removal of such materials from the public domain. On the other hand, groups that advocate for restricted access to information, often in the name of protecting children, tend to view censorship in the much narrower sense of an outright ban on access to materials (Knox, 2014). Though censorship is not a new issue, the unprecedented number of book challenges and bans in the past two years that have predominately targeted materials with themes related to the LGBTQ+ and BIPOC experience (Friedman & Johnson, 2022), highlight the need to better understand the phenomenon of censorship from an ecological perspective. This conceptual paper explores the reasons why people censor and the solutions for protecting library users from censorship through the lens of information behavior, practice, and policy.

CENSORSHIP IS INFORMATION BEHAVIOR

The decision to censor materials may be explained through the lens of information behavior. In particular, theories that explain individual information behavior in its larger societal context are necessary to fully explain the phenomenon of censorship, which occurs at both the policy and personal level. One important theory that satisfies these criteria is Jaeger and Burnett's (2010) theory of information worlds.

The theory of information worlds (Jaeger & Burnett, 2010) states that information forms the small social worlds of individuals, influencing both what information they access, as well as what information they share. Because governments within the larger lifeworld set rules that determine what kind of information may be accessed and shared, information availability has an outsized influence on the information behaviors of individuals, behaviors which are collectively described as information values (Burnett et al., 2014). Information values are further influenced at the small world level by individuals' social roles and the social norms of their communities.

Jaeger and Burnett's theory explains censorship in public and school libraries today, where government bodies, including state education boards and local school and library boards attempt to set policies that restrict access to certain topics and/or materials (Kim, 2022), thus limiting the information behaviors of librarians to seek out and recommend such materials to library users. Librarians are also influenced by the values of the communities to which they belong and serve (i.e. small worlds). This further influences their information behaviors, which may manifest through self-censorship (Kimmel & Hartsfield, 2019).

Recently, a number of cases have made headline news of public libraries being scrutinized over LGBTQ+-themed collections. For example, the Arlington Public Library in Arlington, Texas approved a policy with strict guidelines for Pride month displays, partly in response to concerns from a group of 10 area pastors who stated that LGBTQ+ materials were not aligned to what they described as "family values" (Broussard, 2022). The Pottawatomie Wabaunsee Regional Library in St. Marys, Kansas nearly lost their lease by religiously conservative commissioners who demanded the removal of all LGBTQ+ materials because they claimed that many parents were angry about the inclusion of said content (Mipro, 2022a, 2022b). The Patmos Library in Jamestown Township, Michigan was in fact

defunded over the inclusion of LGBTQ+ books, the result of a successful campaign by a conservative right-wing group (Migdon, 2022).

In all these cases, the ecological perspective reveals a collision course of small social worlds competing for an outsized influence on the larger lifeworld. The pastors in Arlington, Texas and the conservative right-wing group in Jamestown Township, Michigan represent small social worlds with norms and values that conflict with a lifeworld that houses a spectrum of norms and values across its many small worlds. The success of these small worlds' actions on shaping policy in the larger lifeworld demonstrates that policy-based censorship—or small worlds censorship—is the result of the information behaviors of collective individuals who believe that their values are the “right values.” Knox (2015) describes this behavior as censorship by use of the tools of the state through local action.

A potential and deleterious outcome of small worlds censorship may be self-censorship, defined as the intentional decision to avoid the selection of material in response to small worlds norms and values. While it is possible that some librarians may hold the same small worlds values as the groups that seek to censor materials, evidence suggests that they often self-censor controversial materials in an effort to avoid negative interactions and potential challenges by stakeholders (Becnel & Moeller, 2022; Dawkins, 2018). When self-censorship occurs, library users are needlessly harmed through inequitable access to representative materials that reflect their diversity (Daley, 2020; Pekoll, 2020).

CENSORSHIP IS HARMFUL TO ALL

Although not all speech is protected, the First Amendment to the U. S. Constitution guarantees freedom of speech and press necessary for democracy. If small worlds censorship actions lead to the passing of local laws so that certain cultural goods are removed from public institutions and consequently, books are withheld preventing members of the library's community from reading freely, then book banning is harmful in multiple, abusive manners. If left unchecked, censors, including individuals or groups, deliberately seek to limit freedom of speech, thought and expression.

Small worlds censorship also occurs when educators, including teachers and librarians, recite and reuse the same information sources repeatedly over time, creating an environment where information users are left to blindly accept narrow perceptions of the world. Without access to materials presenting various points-of-view, and when individuals do not see themselves in the context of today's society, everyone misses invaluable opportunities for learning through inquiry and investigation, discovery, innovation, and creativity. Thus, censorship may also preclude individuals from developing information literate behaviors (Bates, 2010), i.e., the ways humans interact with information, necessary for inquiry, discerning facts from fiction, seeking truth and reason, building intellectual capacities, and becoming critical thinkers who ask and answer important questions. As Timothy Snyder (2017) points out when addressing how to survive the tyranny of an oppressive government, “[i]t is your ability to discern facts that makes you an individual, and our collective trust in common knowledge that makes us a society.”

Moreover, when States decide what books are morally right or wrong, there is risk of abuse of power resulting in confusing decisions. There are too often exceptions to what the State rules and it becomes difficult to apply the ruling. The State tends to rely on the most influential public perceptions and beliefs that are deemed suitable to those in political power. In anticipation of lawmakers' intentions and/or ruling, some may practice acts of preemptive censorship out of concern that the State will abuse their power. Librarians, who have expertise in instructional librarianship (Benjes-Small & Miller, 2017) should not doubt their expertise and continue to develop library collections, teach information literacy skills, provide information services, and develop library programming to meet the interests and needs of people in the library's community (Dow et al., 2021; Dow & Bushman, 2020).

Overall, censorship behavior causes harm to people of all ages and citizenship status. John Stuart Mill (1859, 2019) asserted that being denied a basic civil liberty is a harmful attack on an individual's right to life. It is harmful to one's quality of life if prevented from speaking, hearing, or reading others' words. Access to books and information is the solution to harmful effects of censorship and is central to missions of libraries.

POLICY IS IMPORTANT IN FIGHTING CENSORSHIP

In response to ongoing attempts by small worlds groups to censor materials in libraries, the American Library Association (2021) released a Statement on Book Censorship. It reads in part,

We are committed to defending the constitutional rights of all individuals, of all ages, to use the resources and services of libraries. We champion and defend the freedom to speak, the freedom to publish, and the freedom to read, as promised by the First Amendment of the Constitution of the United States. (para. 3)

We stand opposed to censorship and any effort to coerce belief, suppress opinion, or punish those whose expression does not conform to what is deemed to be orthodox in history, politics, or belief. The unfettered exchange of ideas is essential to the preservation of a free and democratic society. (para. 4)

To support this statement and to preserve access to information across small worlds, one of the most important tools in the library's fight against censorship is a strong selection policy, which also has the effect of shaping information behavior (Jaeger & Burnett, 2005; Jaeger et al., 2015). Collection development policies, approved by governing boards or other appropriate authorities, provide the basis for equitable acquisition, maintenance and de-acquisition of library materials. Johnson (2018) notes the increasing commonality of collection policies following WWII first in academic libraries then, during the 1950s, in public libraries and in the 1960s in school libraries with the American Association of School Librarians recommending written collection policies in 1961 (p.83).

Policy creation in public libraries is often delegated by state statute to a library board (e.g., Kansas State Statutes, Libraries § 12-1225, 2019; Heritage, Arts, Libraries and Cultural Development § 9-7-404, 2019); and collection policies may be required or strongly recommended by the state libraries overseeing the operation of public libraries within a state (e.g., State Library of Kansas, 2020). Policy in the school library is more commonly approved at the school board level with a resulting system-wide policy, while policy in academic libraries is usually created by a representative library committee and approved by the senior academic officer or senior management committee.

An important benefit of an institutionally approved collections policy is to remove discussion of issues of suitability of materials or censorship of ideas from the actions of a single person to a discussion of institutional beliefs. Collection policies often refer to established statements on equality of access and non-censorship such as the American Library Association's (ALA) Library Bill of Rights (2019), its Right to Read Statement (2004), and the Right to View Statement of the American Film and Video Association (1989).

Moran and Morner (2017) identify four important characteristics that are essential to good policy: that policy is written; that policies are consistent across all operations of the institution; that policy is either flexible to allow for multiple situations or is regularly revised to address changing circumstances; and that policy is clearly differentiated from procedure, thus allowing for some discretion in implementation (p. 105). Good policy therefore ensures consistency of response in similar situations and is also time efficient as the same questions do not have to be addressed from the beginning each time they are raised.

Many school libraries also include in their collections policy a policy for reconsideration of items including the various stages of such a request, the responsibility for responding at each stage, and a final decision-making body, should resolution not be reached during earlier stages. Again, this moves conversations about the appropriateness of items from a personal discussion with an individual to an institutional process where it is the institution that is responsible for defending its policy on equity of access, rather than the task of an individual employee.

Complaints against library and curriculum materials are not new, but as the number of challenges continues to rise (American Library Association, 2022), with complaints based not only on content but on author beliefs, it is essential that all libraries are prepared with written policy that governs the addition or subtraction of materials from the library collection and that the various approval bodies are both aware of the implications of their policy and willing to act upon it in defense of the open access to information.

CONCLUSION

Small worlds censorship is an information behavior that is influenced by social, cultural, and institutional factors. When censorship takes away patrons' rights to read freely, the consequence may be a narrow presentation of perspectives that preclude representation of the diverse community being served. Not only is this a violation of First Amendment rights, it harms individuals' development toward becoming information literate citizens who are able to participate fully in a civilized society. To mitigate the harms of censorship, it is vitally important for libraries to adopt strong selection policies with explicitly stated due process measures.

The theory of information worlds offers a fresh perspective for examining the phenomenon of censorship as information behavior from an ecological perspective. This is particularly relevant as we seek to understand the growing movement of organized small worlds groups that are making headway in their objective to successfully create policy changes at the local and state level to restrict and censor materials that they deem to be inappropriate. It is an alarming trend that violates intellectual freedom, the very foundation of a democratic society.

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